

Research

Role of Cone-Beam Computed Tomography and Radio Visiography in Detecting Additional Canal in Mandibular Anterior Teeth

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Abstract: The most frequent cause of a poor result in mandibular incisor endodontic therapy is the incapacity to identify the existence of a second canal. The location and treatment of mandibular anterior teeth with extra canals have been made easier by improvements in diagnostic instruments, lighting and magnification technologies, endodontic access and detection techniques, and other related fields. This study compared the effectiveness of Radio visiography and Cone-Beam Computed Tomography in identifying extra canals in mandibular anterior teeth. 39 mandibular anterior teeth that met the inclusion and exclusion criteria were chosen in total. The mandibular anterior teeth were scanned using CBCT and periapical x-rays using Radio visiography in parallax view approach in order to discover any new canals. The chi-square test and Kappa correlation coefficient were used to quantitatively assess the agreement between the two approaches. According to the findings, most of the samples only had one canal. Comparing the CBCT analysis to the Radio visiography, more extra canals were found more frequently. In conclusion, compared to RVG collected at different angulations, CBCT can discover more extra canals in mandibular anterior teeth.

Key Words: Additional canal, Radio visiography, Cone-Beam Computed Tomography

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Accepted: 20 January, 2024; **Published:** 22 February, 2024

How to cite this article: Tania Parveen¹, Khaleda Akter, Rahela Yeasmin, Sabequn Nahar-E-Farzana, AKM Bashar, Mozammal Hossain (2024). Role of Cone-Beam Computed Tomography and Radio Visiography in Detecting Additional Canal in Mandibular Anterior Teeth. *North American Academic Research*, 7(1), 112-119. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10968500>

Conflicts of Interest: There are no conflicts to declare.

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Introduction

The morphological diversity of the internal architecture of root canals in permanent human teeth is an essential component for the efficacy of endodontic therapy. The root canal system is complicated, as evidenced by numerous studies, and canals can split, rejoin, and branch. Every tooth's root canal anatomy has a few normal features as well as

many uncommon ones. Understanding these features will help you practice endodontics successfully. A thorough grasp of the root's internal and exterior anatomy would reduce the number of missing roots and root canals during treatment, improving the likelihood of clinical success.(1,2)

Teeth with a single root are thought to be the most amenable to root canal therapy. However, there are several differences in the root canal morphology of mandibular anterior teeth, including the presence of extra canal. Mandibular anterior teeth have a complicated internal morphology despite having a basic exterior appearance. Studies have shown that the lower anterior teeth have different anatomic traits. A range of research, including in vitro and in vivo studies, plain radiography, micro-CT, CBCT, modeling techniques, and tooth clearance techniques, reported the occurrence of extra canals, from 11.5%³ to as high as 68%⁴. Modern endodontic technique has used technical tools including loupes, microscopes, digital radiographs, and Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) in an effort to decrease treatment failure rates and facilitate the finding of additional canals.(3-5)

Conventional intraoral radiography is a clinically sound and extensively utilized technique for identifying canal structure. A direct digital radiography technology called Radio VisioGraphy is currently being used in clinical settings and as an adjunct to alternative radiographic documentation methods that are more advantageous than traditional radiography. Because of its simplicity and speed of use, the patient is exposed to less radiation, the exposure time is shortened, and the image can be handled digitally.(6)

Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) has been available for over ten years as an advancement in diagnostic instruments for dental applications. (5) .Gaining three-dimensional information and seeing a region in three separate planes is helpful to the doctor. Anatomic features are not superimposed when sagittal, coronal, and axial views are combined in CBCT pictures.(6). These benefits give the doctor a clearer picture of the root canal system's intricacies and a deeper comprehension of the system's true anatomy.

The purpose of this work was to use Cone-Beam Computed Tomography and Radio visiography to identify extra root canals in mandibular anterior teeth in order to reduce the frequency of missed root canals and improve endodontic treatment outcomes.

Materials and Methods:

Enrolled in the study were patients undergoing endodontic therapy at Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University's Department of Conservative Dentistry and Endodontics following a comprehensive clinical and radiological evaluation. 39 permanent mandibular incisor teeth that met the requirements for inclusion were chosen. All of the teeth from a patient who met the inclusion criteria were obtained as samples.

Sample size estimation

Sample size was calculated by the following formula:

$$\frac{\{u[\sqrt{\pi(1-\pi)}] + v[\sqrt{\pi_0(1-\pi_0)}]\}}{(\pi - \pi_0)^2}$$

Where,

u= 1.96(table value)

v= 0.84(table value)

π = 0.15 (population proportion under the alternative hypothesis (Assadian et al.7 (2016)

π_0 = 0.35(population proportion under the null hypothesis)

$$\frac{\{1.96[\sqrt{0.15(1-0.15)}] + 0.84[\sqrt{0.35(1-0.35)}]\}}{(0.15 - 0.35)^2}$$

N=30

According to calculation sample size 30. To compensate inadequate data, instrumental fault, illegible data and dropout of the patient 30 was increased to 39.

Radiographic imaging with Radiovisiography

Prior to the radiograph, aseptic precaution was performed. Prior to capturing radiographs, the intraoral digital sensor for each patient was covered with a disposable covering. Every participant wore a lead apron in an effort to reduce radiation exposure from dental radiography. Every patient was taken to the radiograph room to have a periapical x-ray taken using the parallex view technique on Radiovisiography. The patient's x-ray was taken using the Rextar-X radiograph machine. Its integrated lead double shield virtually eliminates leakage from the x-ray source itself, safeguarding operators in close proximity to the apparatus. The Rextar-X was used to take periapical radiographs (RVGs) with exposure parameters of 70 Kv, 2 mA, and exposure times of 0.13 seconds. Three preoperative radiographs were acquired to better visualize the labio-lingual anatomy: two at a mesial and distal angle of about 20°, and one at a 90° angulation to the tooth in the labio-lingual direction. The PC with RVG software installed (Gendex) was used to analyze the RVG images. In order to boost diagnostic capacity, the image enhancing option was also utilized, and standard conditions were met for the radiograph visualization.

CBCT imaging

Cone-Beam Computed Tomography (CBCT) scans were performed on each patient. Cone-Beam CT scans were performed using an additional oral imaging scanner. In a single sweep of the scanner, which spun synchronously through 180° to 360° around the patient's head, a three-dimensional volume of data was collected. The field of view (FOV) is the cylindrical or spherical volume of data that was recorded by the cone-shaped X-ray beam. Dentoalveolar imaging of the tooth was obtained using small FOV units (less than 10 cm). Utilizing a Dell Precision T5400 workstation (Dell, Round Rock, TX) and a 19-inch Dell LCD screen with a resolution of 1,280 × 1,024 pixels in a dark room, the CBCT images were examined using the built-in software (I-Dixel, one-volume viewer 1.5.0). To achieve the best possible visualization, the software's image-processing tool was used to modify the contrast and brightness of the photos.

Results

Of the 39 teeth inspected, 14 (or 35.9%) showed evidence of an additional canal on CBCT, while 6 (15.4%) showed evidence of an additional canal on RVG. When compared to RVG, the statistical analysis showed that the CBCT demonstrated a much higher detection of extra canal. There was a significant difference (p value 0.001) between the evaluation groups (CBCT and RVG). In terms of the canal structure, CBCT observations revealed that type I was present in 25 teeth (64.1%), while type III was seen in 14 teeth (35.1%). However, when examined by RVG, type I was discovered in 33 teeth (84.6%), and type III in 6 teeth (15.4%). A Chi square test was used to examine the relationship between the kind of canal layout determined by CBCT and the type determined by RVG. There was a significant difference (p value 0.001) between the evaluation groups (CBCT and RVG) (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Periapical x-ray taken in three different angulation by RVG (Upper). Axial section of CBCT showing the additional canal in mandibular anterior teeth (Middle). Sagittal section of CBCT showing the Type III canal configuration (Lower).

Table 1: Distribution of the study sample by No. of canal by CBCT (n=39)

No. of canal by CBCT	Number of sample	Percentage
1	25	64.1
2	14	35.9

Table 2: Distribution of the study sample by No. of canal by RVG (n=39)

No. of canal by RVG	Number of sample	Percentage
1	33	84.6
2	6	15.4

Table 3: Association between No. of canal by CBCT with No. of canal by RVG of the study sample (n=39)

No. of canal by RVG	No. of canal by CBCT				Kappa agreement	p value
	1		2			
	n	%	N	%		
1	25	100	8	57.1	0.490	0.001s
2	0	0	6	42.9		

s=significant

Table 4: Association between Type of canal configuration by CBCT with Type of configuration by RVG of the study sample (n=39)

Type of configuration by RVG	Type of configuration by CBCT				Kappa agreement	p value
	Type-I		Type-III			
	n	%	N	%		
Type-I	25	100	8	57.1	0.490	0.001s
Type-III	0	0	6	42.9		

s=significant

Discussion

While the majority of modern studies use computed tomography techniques, earlier studies that looked into the internal morphology of mandibular incisors used radiography, sectioning, modeling, and cleaning techniques. They have all helped to produce a thorough anatomical map of permanent mandibular incisors, illustrating the complexity of the internal morphology of these teeth and the need for varying Vertucci's categorization. (8)

In this study, the methods for identifying extra canals in lower anterior teeth using CBCT and RVG are compared. The current study's findings verified that, as compared to RVG, CBCT was more successful in identifying new canals.

35.9% of mandibular anterior teeth in our study had an extra canal, which has been commonly noted in other studies conducted worldwide. (9-12) Using Radio visiography, it was discovered in this study that there was 15.4% of additional canal frequency, which was also discovered in the work by Oliveira et al. (2008)(13).

In the current investigation, digital radiography yielded lower canal numbers than those reported by CBCT. This was also mentioned by Matherne et al. (2008)14 in their investigation comparing the identification of the root canal system using digital radiography using photostimulable phosphor plate (PSP), charged coupled device (CCD), and CBCT.

Such findings can be attributed to the fact that while observing a CBCT image, numerous and minor anatomical intricacies such as dentinal septa or calcified bridges can be indistinguishable with a separating root canal wall. On the other hand, as stated previously the canal counts reported by digital radiography was low which can be explained by the fact that detection of minor anatomical complexities through the two-dimensional radiographic image even with angular modifications is difficult and can be misleading even for experienced practitioners.

Vertucci's categorization was used in this study to assess the root canal configuration. According to this study, Vertucci's type I root canal configuration—which has a single canal with a single orifice that ends in a single apical foramen—is the most common root canal configuration for human mandibular incisors. This arrangement has been regularly noted in numerous studies conducted all across the world. (9-11)

Conclusion

This study's findings suggest that CBCT, as opposed to RVG conducted at a different angulation, can detect more extra canals in mandibular anterior teeth. In order to visualize additional root canals and evaluate the anatomy of the internal root canals, teeth with complex preoperative radiographs should undergo CBCT.

Author Contributions: At first page.

Approval: All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

Funding: This study is supported by research grant for the student of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University.

Institutional Review Board Statement: This research protocol was approved by the committee and permission for the study was taken from the Institutional Review Board (IRB) of Bangabandhu Sheikh Mujib Medical University (BSMMU/2021/8578).

Informed Consent Statement: Yes

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable

Acknowledgments: Not Mentioned.

Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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